

v-jun avian sarcoma virus 17 oncogene homolog / Jun
proto-oncogene, AP-1 transcription factor subunit (JUN) :
Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in
WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

JUN encode the transcription factor Jun. The structure of activator protein (AP1) is a heterodimer composed of proteins belonging to the c-FOS, c-JUN, ATF and JDP families. Both JUN and its heterodimerization partners in AP1 formation, are subject to regulation by diverse extracellular stimuli, like peptide growth factors, pro-inflammatory cytokines, oxidative and other forms of cellular stress, and UV irradiation. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 JUN related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for JUN-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

Keywords: Sensitivity analysis, Support vector ranking, Hilbert Schmidt

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr JUN comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

¹Aspects of unpublished work were presented in a poster session at Cell Symposia: Technology. Biology. Data Science, 9-11 October 2016, Berkeley, California, USA.

1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3 (= 57155)$ combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search done by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order JUN related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination, then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. v-jun avian sarcoma virus 17 oncogene homolog / Jun proto-oncogene, AP-1 transcription factor subunit (JUN)

Maki et al. [4] show that biologically active molecular clones of avian sarcoma virus 17 (ASV 17) contain a replication-defective proviral genome of 3.5 kilobases (kb), that retains partial gag and env sequences, which flank a cell-derived putative oncogene of 0.93 kb, termed jun. jun lacks preserved coding domains of tyrosine-specific protein kinases and the probable transformation-specific protein in ASV 17-transformed cells is a 55-kDa gag-jun fusion product. Angel et al. [5] show that binding of the human transcription factor JUN/AP1 to a conserved 8 bp nucleotide sequence (TRE) is responsible for increased transcription of different cellular genes in response to tumor promoters, such as TPA, and serum factors. Enhanced JUN/AP1 activity in TPA-stimulated cells is regulated by two different mechanisms: a posttranslational event acting on preexisting JUN/AP1 molecules, and transcriptional activation of JUN gene expression leading to an increase in the total amount of JUN/AP1. Their results demonstrated that JUN transcription was directly stimulated by its own gene product.

c-JUN was originally isolated as the cellular homolog of v-JUN, as stated in Wisdom et al. [6]. They state that c-JUN is a component of AP1, which is activated by a wide variety of extracellular stimuli. The regulation of c-JUN is complex and involves both increases in the levels of c-JUN protein as well as phosphorylation of specific serines (63 and 73) by JUN N-terminal kinase (JNK). They used fibroblasts derived from c-JUN null embryos to define the role of c-JUN in two separate processes, namely, cell growth and apoptosis.

Hess et al. [7] state that The AP1 transcription factor is mainly composed of JUN, FOS and ATF protein dimers. It mediates gene regulation in response to a many physiological and pathological stimuli, including cytokines, growth factors, stress signals, bacterial and viral infections, as well as oncogenic stimuli.

I present 3rd order combinations of JUN with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [8]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [8].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one

recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7_1C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a

strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 JUN-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [9]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [10] and martinez implementation in Martinez [11] and Baudin et al. [12]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested JUN-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving JUN were obtained from a full set of ${}^{71}C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of FOSL1-JUN-X combinations

The FOS and JUN families of eukaryotic transcription factors heterodimerize to form complexes capable of binding 5'-TGAGTCA-3' DNA elements. Glover and Harrison [13] determined the X-ray crystal structure of a heterodimer of the bZIP regions of c-FOS and c-JUN bound to DNA. Both subunits formed continuous α -helices. The

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DKK1-JUN-SENP2	3	13146	45291	34681	42815	FZD5-JUN-TLE2	33	2696	2557	55511	23342
DVL2-JUN-SENP2	40	7571	46728	17699	4151	DKK1-JUN-LRP5	48	627	56508	43115	37922
DVL2-JUN-TCF7L1	50	34646	43296	24980	5047	DKK1-JUN-SFRP4	53	1275	44566	37789	42099
DKK1-JUN-TLE2	55	1113	26078	37591	53405	DKK1-JUN-WNT2B	56	5221	53944	55625	44612
DKK1-JUN-WNT2	58	1936	43652	35916	55311	DKK1-JUN-TCF7L1	67	33647	49514	43728	45939
FZD5-JUN-WNT2	71	4401	38543	47328	33190	FZD5-JUN-WNT4	79	8704	42294	52216	15657
DVL2-JUN-TLE2	87	42627	5285	18305	31287	FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	96	24278	50801	44288	10781
FZD5-JUN-FBXW4	97	13039	25922	48154	41051	FZD5-JUN-RHOU	105	12942	56571	25707	3718
FRZB-JUN-SENP2	109	12704	33983	8160	2937	CTNNBIP1-JUN-RHOU	119	11333	54553	37428	52492
DKK1-JUN-FBXW4	129	11896	24951	31819	36572	DVL2-JUN-FBXW4	135	26880	12581	12861	8554
DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	178	24966	37758	33223	9256	DVL2-JUN-WNT4	203	51324	39998	14159	3459
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT2	206	3834	45427	33327	6238	DKK1-JUN-RHOU	210	3670	42736	27568	47765
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	218	3236	51191	53120	2659	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2R1A	222	17930	41664	52992	44848
CTNNBIP1-JUN-KREMEN1	241	6571	55388	29592	14471	DVL2-JUN-WNT2	252	43710	32464	4614	34311
DKK1-JUN-PPP2R1A	267	12255	56230	48454	54215	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SFRP4	282	1303	44436	32290	6337
FZD5-JUN-WNT5A	284	6962	43259	53869	10481	DKK1-JUN-WNT3A	289	6120	44241	52638	12402
DVL2-JUN-PITX2	293	27343	32163	42607	21387	DVL2-JUN-TLE1	306	36089	30012	17193	22195
DKK1-JUN-WNT4	316	926	46570	28834	28365	DVL2-JUN-WNT3A	322	31939	32028	29113	4760
DKK1-JUN-TCF7	337	19121	54724	39273	38745	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	348	1924	32815	54426	36260
DVL2-JUN-WNT2B	350	44599	38931	37935	16078	FZD5-JUN-TCF7	367	15943	33055	41015	49415
DKK1-JUN-PPP2CA	408	27394	50340	28816	37806	DKK1-JUN-TLE1	417	16467	28915	26740	32148
EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	445	18545	22047	46724	18178	FZD5-JUN-TLE1	448	23448	36104	54093	45715
CTNNBIP1-JUN-SENP2	451	45193	55478	33408	6827	FOSL1-JUN-SENP2	458	25557	50663	10786	1378
FRZB-JUN-WNT2	478	2085	21294	5583	18722	DVL2-JUN-PPP2CA	504	43997	37157	2445	3613
DVL2-JUN-TCF7	544	30871	41999	26197	8304	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PITX2	546	6389	45937	54346	11119
DVL2-JUN-PPP2R1A	555	45651	45029	17035	30388	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	570	14118	6423	19469	36536
DKK1-JUN-LRP6	617	2273	42860	25885	1791	FZD5-JUN-SLC9A3R1	625	5957	34667	52133	12374
CTNNBIP1-JUN-TCF7	674	24941	33229	25262	14247	FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	676	35197	23478	4515	23224
DVL1-JUN-WNT2B	696	13741	48925	47783	49704	CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP5	697	1403	32050	45845	13691
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	748	50033	38113	50412	44660	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	764	1040	837	11709	30876
DVL2-JUN-WIF1	788	37918	18319	11932	34672	FBXW11-JUN-WNT2B	795	49304	52661	53929	54016
FBXW2-JUN-WNT4	806	26430	56620	37987	55952	FZD8-JUN-WNT2B	814	45692	37162	26955	54126
CSNK1D-JUN-LEF1	823	6859	47543	11454	29458	CXXC4-JUN-SENP2	843	21048	50347	6595	9660
CSNK1G1-JUN-SENP2	855	23957	55112	11084	3256	DVL2-JUN-WNT5A	871	37929	52159	30056	48277
FRAT1-JUN-SENP2	876	27146	34459	14780	13983	CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	881	1789	43156	41625	53423
FBXW11-JUN-LRP5	885	23634	45785	27639	45330	FZD1-JUN-WNT2	886	20644	39928	4484	8707
BCL9-JUN-TCF7L1	889	18626	55169	44931	2804	DKK1-JUN-PITX2	913	6407	42538	52798	634
FRZB-JUN-TCF7L1	932	26973	39828	31513	3210	DKK1-JUN-SFRP1	961	1935	26970	33204	47981
FBXW11-JUN-SFRP4	964	21656	28145	38980	53582	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	971	1353	33173	6860	26690
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	996	16387	31797	50574	23742	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	1000	17132	38816	29827	1621
FZD1-JUN-TLE2	1075	7630	4614	20083	41713	FBXW11-JUN-SENP2	1078	21114	46139	41233	39344
CSNK1G1-JUN-WNT2	1087	1305	52762	5894	31347	CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT3A	1110	7698	46119	54862	31125
CSNK1G1-JUN-TCF7L1	1134	10933	47748	13909	25134	CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	1138	13192	17971	6537	17461
DVL2-JUN-SFRP1	1150	43616	21933	13995	37221	DAAM1-JUN-WNT2B	1152	51606	37010	32012	42370
CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2CA	1160	17287	25595	27276	6859	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	1177	38200	26202	16198	34929
CCND1-JUN-SFRP4	1212	40676	36610	54521	54939	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	1227	27649	37384	31940	7577
FZD7-JUN-WNT3A	1250	17078	32637	21100	43381	FBXW2-JUN-SENP2	1253	32758	51631	42897	55749
CCND1-JUN-PITX2	1260	51205	42011	18763	52917	GSK3B-JUN-TLE1	1271	40084	30251	26212	40565
FBXW11-JUN-TLE2	1285	29879	11548	36884	55887	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	1308	4014	25558	7639	24982
CTNNBIP1-JUN-FBXW4	1320	15975	24670	37193	14093	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	1340	27624	17009	49472	50306
JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	1341	24994	40582	4657	37476	BCL9-JUN-TLE2	1353	1767	14711	51640	5284
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	1362	50934	48125	55357	25009	CSNK1G1-JUN-TLE2	1365	2675	25875	17296	52928
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	1379	21025	34076	34379	37036	FRZB-JUN-PPP2CA	1383	13534	31714	933	1610
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	1397	18158	39442	41838	15514	DKK1-JUN-LEF1	1407	345	39847	38268	15426
FRZB-JUN-SLC9A3R1	1409	6059	10710	25355	42497	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	1479	1306	37107	54515	12375
FZD1-JUN-SFRP4	1493	24355	34044	13135	44616	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	1496	10929	38139	43065	17470
CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP6	1499	4675	42275	26834	8608	CCND1-JUN-PPP2CA	1525	10554	35624	43398	54711
FBXW11-JUN-TCF7L1	1526	26632	46567	48986	51386	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	1542	4890	20754	29478	5342
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	1561	16594	47993	27451	26786	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	1571	14622	52390	27682	7035
CTBP2-JUN-TLE2	1591	46301	4452	35914	13872	CSNK1A1-JUN-TCF7L1	1599	2840	51813	45452	5619
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT4	1605	6379	54822	28948	10594	FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	1626	39276	40450	30425	12391
DVL1-JUN-SENP2	1636	27735	49539	26023	46168	FZD1-JUN-WNT2B	1648	10746	47422	41725	9336
BCL9-JUN-RHOU	1653	6622	56085	44704	6331	DAAM1-JUN-SENP2	1658	50069	38838	15921	52559

Table 1: Rankings of JUN-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

carboxy-terminal regions form an asymmetric coiled-coil, and the amino-terminal regions make base-specific contacts with DNA in the major groove. Comparison of the two crystallographically distinct protein-DNA complexes showed that the coiled-coil

RANKING @ t_1 USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DKK1-JUN-SEN2	2445	33296	14766	10519	28087	FZD5-JUN-TLE2	18001	2899	23629	42402	48124
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	4462	28972	39208	37581	33219	DKK1-JUN-LRP5	44363	59	7957	31836	12454
DVL2-JUN-TCF7L1	6692	37689	42883	22632	2352	DKK1-JUN-SFRP4	23984	4600	8391	10229	3109
DKK1-JUN-TLE2	10461	10318	33449	28447	40483	DKK1-JUN-WNT2B	23590	25652	38169	27335	22936
DKK1-JUN-WNT2	15958	5371	10742	16568	29068	DKK1-JUN-TCF7L1	11024	26336	26266	38929	770
FZD5-JUN-WNT2	45453	4822	16137	45403	40375	FZD5-JUN-WNT4	28544	6905	45357	25315	15393
DVL2-JUN-TLE2	6307	41319	43004	40157	41574	FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	14265	7847	49848	50707	31671
FZD5-JUN-FBXW4	32588	11252	24483	51441	24264	FZD5-JUN-RHOU	21830	6512	2365	50002	36411
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	1481	18469	38799	27435	28090	CTNNBIP1-JUN-RHOU	47402	8172	34623	51918	36687
DKK1-JUN-FBXW4	36904	13586	2374	17612	12759	DVL2-JUN-FBXW4	26608	26616	1444	12875	15856
DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	13103	30709	32743	48017	27397	DVL2-JUN-WNT4	21779	49475	22727	20132	5205
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT2	42601	8719	44457	18821	49158	DKK1-JUN-RHOU	4232	243	27543	37520	46403
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	35611	92	8244	34065	42310	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2R1A	42662	30325	24952	5762	37211
CTNNBIP1-JUN-KREMEN1	49360	1571	43983	55548	30690	DVL2-JUN-WNT2	26710	49937	37500	33239	22813
DKK1-JUN-PPP2R1A	19726	15606	1085	29841	36603	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SFRP4	50889	5964	52857	23302	32122
FZD5-JUN-WNT5A	8780	13834	37545	56636	50500	DKK1-JUN-WNT3A	10634	402	10397	46299	3270
DVL2-JUN-PITX2	22623	16521	37051	52719	15020	DVL2-JUN-TLE1	36629	36442	30000	29148	8644
DKK1-JUN-WNT4	8806	34	14859	3085	9371	DVL2-JUN-WNT3A	25797	23440	31750	21568	1485
DKK1-JUN-TCF7	4445	24804	23041	23852	12528	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	13399	522	43506	36219	51123
DVL2-JUN-WNT2B	35904	41234	30718	47010	18770	FZD5-JUN-TCF7	13732	2579	35094	27662	15659
DKK1-JUN-PPP2CA	872	31181	33266	21737	30431	DKK1-JUN-TLE1	12635	18611	25341	28339	18891
EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	4639	142	27356	54948	19911	FZD5-JUN-TLE1	12747	18718	33701	39270	7010
CTNNBIP1-JUN-SEN2	42259	50095	40291	21021	34386	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	15271	29847	41615	22047	48378
FRZB-JUN-WNT2	21990	24790	40993	7840	23831	DVL2-JUN-PPP2CA	12969	55374	21200	14940	32734
DVL2-JUN-TCF7	4906	31956	33672	6793	3595	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PITX2	55688	6273	51543	54725	26305
DVL2-JUN-PPP2R1A	7790	48428	6855	9490	40633	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	10181	579	35737	33610	43746
DKK1-JUN-LRP6	26624	5079	13887	46906	27696	FZD5-JUN-SLC9A3R1	39777	3230	20742	34190	14401
CTNNBIP1-JUN-TCF7	41380	25473	25735	11678	41440	FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	21621	33205	53792	38197	10593
DVL1-JUN-WNT2B	44382	6721	23326	56398	1235	CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP5	51735	260	35013	50048	34138
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	28349	55075	50998	56838	16856	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	2337	10507	41107	15818	46481
DVL2-JUN-WIF1	6060	40504	15256	30934	48673	FBXW11-JUN-WNT2B	30736	52338	1286	29236	8641
FBXW2-JUN-WNT4	49067	9843	17416	10298	1111	FZD8-JUN-WNT2B	30397	45061	16498	26458	9398
CSNK1D-JUN-LEF1	20901	8723	38740	12713	27687	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	1851	32478	55139	8858	43014
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	2057	43819	27038	14070	17638	DVL2-JUN-WNT5A	16054	35608	35930	17120	44512
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	8350	32873	42151	5535	36295	CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	7270	2533	37155	46380	45935
FBXW11-JUN-LRP5	46395	5177	29373	22491	4533	FZD1-JUN-WNT2	52622	26168	48248	5592	27125
BCL9-JUN-TCF7L1	24868	22870	36874	19513	1734	DKK1-JUN-PITX2	24208	3989	4050	56945	15274
FRZB-JUN-TCF7L1	9523	51903	25105	20905	20981	DKK1-JUN-SFRP1	15339	875	11803	12204	51585
FBXW11-JUN-SFRP4	17788	9290	3063	40195	1563	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	15539	1611	30933	39991	28813
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	18538	5069	12539	42545	29271	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	5134	9823	24616	52464	27691
FZD1-JUN-TLE2	24688	27343	11195	3015	35208	FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	2521	15541	36470	25945	625
CSNK1G1-JUN-WNT2	10147	5580	32401	33214	37290	CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT3A	24780	5944	45858	50803	13854
CSNK1G1-JUN-TCF7L1	827	11310	28918	27910	3674	CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	14457	30498	1036	36322	33651
DVL2-JUN-SFRP1	10995	46091	46482	41358	52216	DAAMI-JUN-WNT2B	34628	49211	11090	56716	4721
CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2CA	38196	36635	20141	33944	38991	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	35091	47221	26189	44148	8318
CCND1-JUN-SFRP4	38237	25562	52223	10931	1352	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	45992	37553	52601	42751	21986
FZD7-JUN-WNT3A	6578	3907	45657	38691	15081	FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	25289	51870	3972	20307	1098
CCND1-JUN-PITX2	44312	43519	25962	49672	2955	GSK3B-JUN-TLE1	21678	43855	47673	19227	7501
FBXW11-JUN-TLE2	12624	12939	27323	12238	19853	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	8489	12877	51306	12233	26552
CTNNBIP1-JUN-FBXW4	38357	26382	25017	7941	22281	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	53699	39669	27414	16988	3729
JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	2091	9953	10078	26860	57045	BCL9-JUN-TLE2	25015	9243	46821	14241	21549
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	15052	38950	15637	52389	3265	CSNK1G1-JUN-TLE2	3633	15390	39684	2796	27092
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	2896	16477	22826	15141	21339	FRZB-JUN-PPP2CA	5873	49297	3845	20493	26715
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	36423	32144	31736	45585	462	DKK1-JUN-LEF1	15292	323	25256	25883	39611
FRZB-JUN-SLC9A3R1	34630	15041	47309	7650	16482	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	42099	14135	52254	57017	24935
FZD1-JUN-SFRP4	44475	27425	5889	28115	8946	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	15268	3842	31367	43633	53074
CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP6	41800	8865	4751	4915	48545	CCND1-JUN-PPP2CA	40595	14062	3971	9088	1571
FBXW11-JUN-TCF7L1	5238	17905	26014	9636	4500	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	37744	27522	48171	53533	24924
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	5069	16399	50288	29076	25853	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	6491	2240	25073	41585	18357
CTBP2-JUN-TLE2	2322	40968	49108	5379	22516	CSNK1A1-JUN-TCF7L1	22985	1629	17522	50991	17011
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT4	39260	388	36889	17634	53412	FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	25869	45197	28755	12226	10788
DVL1-JUN-SEN2	17916	15346	45039	2157	2784	FZD1-JUN-WNT2B	49546	6083	15156	54576	28886
BCL9-JUN-RHOU	27668	3483	7713	42147	31193	DAAMI-JUN-SEN2	28479	51658	5776	9253	6064

Table 2: Rankings of JUN-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

is flexibly joined to the basic regions and that the FOS-JUN heterodimer did not recognize the asymmetric 5'-TGAGTCA-3' recognition element in a unique orientation.

Heterodimerization among the basic-leucine zipper (bZIP) proteins or among the basic-helix/loop/helix-leucine zipper (bHLHZip) proteins confers a multitude of combi-

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DKK1-JUN-SEN2	754	9372	11904	1076	33385	FZD5-JUN-TLE2	41573	48046	35361	54860	7334
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	13471	27115	21910	19735	56433	DKK1-JUN-LRP5	48850	11594	39630	41378	23052
DVL2-JUN-TCF7L1	31682	50919	38373	29294	10924	DKK1-JUN-SFRP4	2159	46694	9618	10954	53360
DKK1-JUN-TLE2	51285	19906	29994	46512	5324	DKK1-JUN-WNT2B	55363	40120	46822	38204	3471
DKK1-JUN-WNT2	1793	17173	10372	18936	53659	DKK1-JUN-TCF7L1	54195	13967	44741	41708	6796
FZD5-JUN-WNT2	5734	51317	12612	516	52072	FZD5-JUN-WNT4	10431	52363	25511	23980	54325
DVL2-JUN-TLE2	37775	50662	42118	36079	5151	FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	40950	45002	28772	48247	9854
FZD5-JUN-FBXW4	38132	1495	38878	55550	15245	FZD5-JUN-RHOU	34450	36279	38790	52137	4153
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	12004	43333	28019	17227	24299	CTNNBIP1-JUN-RHOU	42622	37205	47514	55158	1108
DKK1-JUN-FBXW4	55004	10538	47561	46222	3807	DVL2-JUN-FBXW4	37995	50015	47979	42759	40551
DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	30808	34898	33501	52840	6443	DVL2-JUN-WNT4	16345	10299	13394	21121	55056
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT2	11911	1262	6891	21217	41714	DKK1-JUN-RHOU	36718	6757	39502	48964	14725
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	20453	50366	17707	8188	42484	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2R1A	55954	42703	38291	39039	13787
CTNNBIP1-JUN-KREMEN1	42377	46499	47863	48423	9908	DVL2-JUN-WNT2	16689	9003	10414	13155	52714
DKK1-JUN-PPP2R1A	57057	38094	40889	35645	26618	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SFRP4	16570	24584	750	1029	26322
FZD5-JUN-WNT5A	46652	4870	31639	33192	2907	DKK1-JUN-WNT3A	51531	12300	46409	53700	3796
DVL2-JUN-PITX2	23671	1038	12434	27999	54466	DVL2-JUN-TLE1	19381	6455	15016	21061	52059
DKK1-JUN-WNT4	2160	6260	8008	12977	38088	DVL2-JUN-WNT3A	35727	49416	40820	44967	1537
DKK1-JUN-TCF7	2980	42733	12423	15481	50307	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	22701	20169	18383	5021	52969
DVL2-JUN-WNT2B	40463	48141	46668	43995	4463	FZD5-JUN-TCF7	21221	30391	25873	1692	44909
DKK1-JUN-PPP2CA	98	19110	16349	21529	30627	DKK1-JUN-TLE1	5879	37800	27150	10679	51804
EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	11605	22398	6349	16123	55238	FZD5-JUN-TLE1	15555	9196	21799	2297	49839
CTNNBIP1-JUN-SEN2	15007	40205	17451	2535	40407	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	51877	55400	52885	34018	3734
FRZB-JUN-WNT2	18619	2162	17358	26907	22142	DVL2-JUN-PPP2CA	24259	24689	15208	7592	48248
DVL2-JUN-TCF7	25445	6256	18825	27882	46274	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PITX2	11329	1937	10201	6114	40219
DVL2-JUN-PPP2R1A	32860	32858	41918	49574	8979	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	1610	17601	24757	13846	37085
DKK1-JUN-LRP6	889	49598	15333	19395	28530	FZD5-JUN-SLC9A3R1	19660	8438	20540	9033	50969
CTNNBIP1-JUN-TCF7	6098	7522	16157	8323	52544	FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	8549	16613	14863	6104	42450
DVL1-JUN-WNT2B	55129	18060	30213	42553	11665	CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP5	52013	50795	51766	42741	16689
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	19630	54721	9834	10848	22067	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	47401	2576	46879	53365	10616
DVL2-JUN-WIF1	15451	4813	8548	10559	52944	FBXW11-JUN-WNT2B	29211	26070	34684	38249	15818
FBXW2-JUN-WNT4	6945	6699	21970	13741	36379	FZD8-JUN-WNT2B	53721	5288	39583	33282	9288
CSNK1D-JUN-LEF1	25658	26247	28008	9195	29514	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	8825	8401	12932	7871	27023
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	49955	51075	54767	43231	2180	DVL2-JUN-WNT5A	40789	46792	43770	36077	2170
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	10491	7985	11945	814	56174	CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	43332	26892	49071	46614	1986
FBXW11-JUN-LRP5	29144	55408	44273	48284	18254	FZD1-JUN-WNT2	22633	26709	17508	18911	53158
BCL9-JUN-TCF7L1	10128	54591	19355	15272	44855	DKK1-JUN-PITX2	2939	11664	23494	19389	44598
FRZB-JUN-TCF7L1	43224	53526	30364	36886	9096	DKK1-JUN-SFRP1	56402	47506	45269	56075	23790
FBXW11-JUN-SFRP4	26958	10929	24740	8133	48845	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	33040	7608	43755	38567	13643
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	49067	35754	42264	40921	9123	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	4213	41297	24152	15364	47738
FZD1-JUN-TLE2	44268	55094	42586	33377	6664	FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	27619	7495	18431	13804	56624
CSNK1G1-JUN-WNT2	43215	54139	50622	48011	1250	CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT3A	47078	14611	51686	48296	5008
CSNK1G1-JUN-TCF7L1	6017	14337	20145	21380	48232	CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	49484	2831	37278	49282	3845
DVL2-JUN-SFRP1	43635	30176	35239	37444	736	DAAM1-JUN-WNT2B	52248	43893	48230	50763	39740
CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2CA	1200	14488	18797	18145	43428	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	21027	9576	20703	24611	44741
CCND1-JUN-SFRP4	20932	24429	19033	3104	41522	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	22481	35127	9927	24826	33487
FZD7-JUN-WNT3A	1386	53880	25449	20632	45908	FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	10475	4057	14601	2973	45279
CCND1-JUN-PITX2	17592	41812	11511	4995	53682	GSK3B-JUN-TLE1	8247	452	12235	2187	37512
FBXW11-JUN-TLE2	28842	50663	44769	54898	3936	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	7686	54368	19771	7870	53296
CTNNBIP1-JUN-FBXW4	40631	32924	56400	56117	31184	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	23517	23502	15073	18409	44877
JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	3800	11209	18229	255	32111	BCL9-JUN-TLE2	3148	9305	24717	4483	54658
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	25910	36673	28134	15173	40843	CSNK1G1-JUN-TLE2	6833	1066	4928	11587	56004
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	1115	20606	6634	9559	44618	FRZB-JUN-PPP2CA	7300	14667	7614	23131	10832
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	9143	45568	15142	2009	35636	DKK1-JUN-LEF1	8362	45451	17549	15763	34051
FRZB-JUN-SLC9A3R1	21722	36003	21129	27499	26935	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	29544	47341	44123	52018	7644
FZD1-JUN-SFRP4	9479	1152	20120	8827	46342	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	13879	27252	8058	10543	55180
CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP6	16607	13114	2882	13685	40184	CCND1-JUN-PPP2CA	23078	52819	9647	2403	50956
FBXW11-JUN-TCF7L1	29061	55371	38660	56451	2416	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	10579	5753	10670	19639	21636
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	56040	37157	50497	47616	12624	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	6923	4884	26325	13483	55790
CTBP2-JUN-TLE2	45238	40887	44003	32561	49556	CSNK1A1-JUN-TCF7L1	48736	28417	29151	42720	4277
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT4	18138	13025	5771	2388	39991	FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	43935	48115	50408	53433	8865
DVL1-JUN-SEN2	1057	37410	27437	23571	26894	FZD1-JUN-WNT2B	34517	30754	39634	38168	4014
BCL9-JUN-RHOU	13091	32869	21205	19079	54663	DAAM1-JUN-SEN2	17437	48030	18701	23987	45424

Table 3: Rankings of JUN-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

national activities to these transcription factors. To further examine the function of the bHLHZip protein, USF, Pognonec et al. [14] found cellular bZip protein, FRA1/FOSL1 to directly interact with USF using the yeast two-hybrid system. Expression of exogenous USF led to a decrease in AP1-dependent transcription in F9 cells and co-

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
DKK1-JUN-SEN2	39293	26785	2472	17869	34742	FZD5-JUN-TLE2	45101	44732	49549	7443	22376
DVL2-JUN-SEN2	35230	56370	12983	26309	6576	DKK1-JUN-LRP5	8488	42089	3935	5674	24381
DVL2-JUN-TCF7L1	38504	39014	8620	32892	40588	DKK1-JUN-SFRP4	34594	21804	25466	30057	51482
DKK1-JUN-TLE2	10057	27588	1220	31857	31811	DKK1-JUN-WNT2B	16474	6155	31575	3599	21858
DKK1-JUN-WNT2	21281	7585	9715	13230	39907	DKK1-JUN-TCF7L1	11702	2034	13336	29520	36553
FZD5-JUN-WNT2	25240	24032	52661	27883	21598	FZD5-JUN-WNT4	19865	9292	48700	12138	52601
DVL2-JUN-TLE2	45577	28542	22192	43080	24490	FZD5-JUN-KREMEN1	50060	49716	44146	14490	16078
FZD5-JUN-FBXW4	52922	41805	48790	3712	42515	FZD5-JUN-RHOU	47751	36706	49382	38988	21511
FRZB-JUN-SEN2	4353	41972	31373	42600	6952	CTNNBIP1-JUN-RHOU	45818	54814	30791	4085	30728
DKK1-JUN-FBXW4	17118	2212	3560	29990	25976	DVL2-JUN-FBXW4	36950	1214	4840	47247	9512
DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1	35856	27962	6728	43550	27735	DVL2-JUN-WNT4	12922	5091	28902	26178	19271
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT2	9051	26257	51811	12974	46154	DKK1-JUN-RHOU	6220	29190	3055	27518	42579
DKK1-JUN-PYGO1	18955	10082	6546	24602	4336	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2R1A	53037	53341	798	1131	42840
CTNNBIP1-JUN-KREMEN1	18623	46010	5144	39503	49383	DVL2-JUN-WNT2	33688	13863	40309	7310	23857
DKK1-JUN-PPP2R1A	44652	4023	140	29083	28080	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SFRP4	8181	25302	22170	2710	24546
FZD5-JUN-WNT5A	37922	45149	3248	18094	8459	DKK1-JUN-WNT3A	8769	37818	1990	21743	36662
DVL2-JUN-PITX2	36525	53951	49133	9931	6910	DVL2-JUN-TLE1	32299	34232	29411	30046	13256
DKK1-JUN-WNT4	292	3863	10616	27487	47309	DVL2-JUN-WNT3A	48177	29325	2623	32807	56119
DKK1-JUN-TCF7	3580	5786	28745	14691	47110	FZD5-JUN-PYGO1	21220	21257	46978	36871	44319
DVL2-JUN-WNT2B	50622	8656	8692	8248	41711	FZD5-JUN-TCF7	31467	27572	43715	37490	33576
DKK1-JUN-PPP2CA	16976	18784	14132	11492	11442	DKK1-JUN-TLE1	35552	23005	2652	29560	46025
EP300-JUN-KREMEN1	32750	6325	30769	2643	11537	FZD5-JUN-TLE1	27245	16368	48791	27309	50250
CTNNBIP1-JUN-SEN2	24218	24078	19550	5942	13375	FOSL1-JUN-SEN2	11684	1590	49191	41693	56255
FRZB-JUN-WNT2	14499	46525	53139	47393	43695	DVL2-JUN-PPP2CA	35923	8438	19130	28183	37748
DVL2-JUN-TCF7	9145	11851	54475	18119	46069	CTNNBIP1-JUN-PITX2	22154	22207	5596	2608	22098
DVL2-JUN-PPP2R1A	47799	3904	40852	41830	40087	JUN-PYGO1-WNT3A	8462	12690	54986	11759	6706
DKK1-JUN-LRP6	1904	586	17116	25580	22711	FZD5-JUN-SLC9A3R1	7989	20917	50796	34445	46189
CTNNBIP1-JUN-TCF7	21302	20350	23300	8362	15547	FRAT1-JUN-WNT2	17000	17285	9957	1367	55436
DVL1-JUN-WNT2B	17087	18170	1138	3417	39507	CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP5	56066	45453	8760	2079	21250
FRAT1-JUN-PITX2	12383	53362	24248	28478	2424	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	54851	48414	34147	40148	9323
DVL2-JUN-WIF1	37056	9990	21687	38184	36567	FBXW11-JUN-WNT2B	33659	37203	20213	9874	32143
FBXW2-JUN-WNT4	35429	42647	44788	43088	49776	FZD8-JUN-WNT2B	47390	29843	6652	5804	30618
CSNK1D-JUN-LEF1	36389	9478	48851	37502	3819	CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	45684	29715	54947	15159	18626
CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2	53562	32056	34894	40476	27708	DVL2-JUN-WNT5A	56096	6903	2980	44469	43199
FRAT1-JUN-SEN2	25462	55027	16547	2227	53156	CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	56140	21552	3493	38523	19065
FBXW11-JUN-LRP5	25964	2876	26897	41525	31316	FZD1-JUN-WNT2	2396	55693	14661	50347	54864
BCL9-JUN-TCF7L1	54085	54334	41976	50786	4157	DKK1-JUN-PITX2	12302	18067	6655	22598	48385
FRZB-JUN-TCF7L1	55641	47527	46379	33807	23058	DKK1-JUN-SFRP1	27403	584	1550	24740	22043
FBXW11-JUN-SFRP4	18627	25907	44228	8331	4031	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	14950	38582	26056	22260	14906
FOSL1-JUN-TCF7	9174	53008	50222	47253	30596	FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1	7033	46161	34317	46961	357
FZD1-JUN-TLE2	49976	26538	4673	41523	8517	FBXW11-JUN-SEN2	9156	15077	6177	1681	2691
CSNK1G1-JUN-WNT2	26112	36147	34970	53598	32760	CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT3A	56225	30611	13354	42578	38675
CSNK1G1-JUN-TCF7L1	20659	31359	42235	11222	25258	CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	54886	34793	20190	5710	9414
DVL2-JUN-SFRP1	47779	49816	5357	44152	18937	DAAM1-JUN-WNT2B	54799	36164	2157	26110	26593
CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2CA	35131	50326	1387	2781	52171	FRAT1-JUN-SFRP4	5493	26134	6285	2741	55395
CCND1-JUN-SFRP4	840	12360	38515	53202	51681	CTNNBIP1-JUN-SLC9A3R1	34854	45056	8371	4563	2100
FZD7-JUN-WNT3A	2485	10637	49466	56154	32099	FBXW2-JUN-SEN2	44868	6548	55912	21346	1004
CCND1-JUN-PITX2	26952	23887	45413	42573	55139	GSK3B-JUN-TLE1	27193	31279	43425	49869	910
FBXW11-JUN-TLE2	31586	1673	33776	1670	43828	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	13812	15293	47877	3185	27486
CTNNBIP1-JUN-FBXW4	49568	36886	4548	11262	41237	DIXDC1-JUN-FBXW4	4436	32111	14584	49771	47714
JUN-PYGO1-TLE2	39043	10881	55054	5405	2750	BCL9-JUN-TLE2	11112	24571	24842	54455	4870
CCND3-JUN-PYGO1	1105	3178	49390	42434	50732	CSNK1G1-JUN-TLE2	3654	15612	6612	7680	23323
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	11066	2375	24218	5640	51093	FRZB-JUN-PPP2CA	13541	57069	53146	52693	38925
DIXDC1-JUN-TCF7L1	217	3466	4432	50780	14710	DKK1-JUN-LEF1	4794	48265	3692	28488	39033
FRZB-JUN-SLC9A3R1	11072	37219	48670	53602	1700	FOSL1-JUN-PITX2	6068	2098	52232	48612	54047
FZD1-JUN-SFRP4	19225	52148	32337	47804	47331	CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	19004	24107	54656	40210	53966
CTNNBIP1-JUN-LRP6	728	9347	30644	17025	37953	CCND1-JUN-PPP2CA	42904	56795	22325	53788	5368
FBXW11-JUN-TCF7L1	34037	37042	29608	18961	34201	FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A	50101	9229	37322	47023	17545
CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	55451	45389	163	3252	9752	CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1	21900	17437	22609	16420	7910
CTBP2-JUN-TLE2	26731	5668	29388	38522	27440	CSNK1A1-JUN-TCF7L1	56402	21678	40854	35544	40582
CTNNBIP1-JUN-WNT4	8571	16635	1790	9191	55418	FRAT1-JUN-TCF7L1	52500	31836	3000	12107	9211
DVL1-JUN-SEN2	41505	4238	15845	27786	44253	FZD1-JUN-WNT2B	40470	56406	19457	34145	8292
BCL9-JUN-RHOU	6886	57071	51774	45461	27328	DAAM1-JUN-SEN2	5807	25244	21110	19946	32160

Table 4: Rankings of JUN-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

expression of exogenous FRA1/FOSL1 restored the AP1 activity in a dose-dependent manner.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for FOSL1 along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - FOSL1-JUN-TCF7, FOSL1-

JUN-SEN2, FOSL1-JUN-TCF7L1, FOSL1-JUN-PITX2 and FOSL1-JUN-WNT3A. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of BCL-JUN-X combinations

Na et al. [15] show that BCL3 stimulates the AP1 transactivation, either alone or in conjunction with transcription integrators steroid receptor coactivator-1 and CREB-binding protein/p300. Using the yeast and mammalian two-hybrid tests as well as glutathione S-transferase pull-down assays, they demonstrated that the C-terminal 158 residues of BCL3 exhibited an autonomous transactivation function and interacted with specific subregions of the AP1 components c-JUN and c-FOS, CREB-binding protein/p300, and steroid receptor coactivator-1.

Expression of the Blimp1 transcription factor which is critical for promoting B cell differentiation into plasma cells, is repressed by BCL6. Vasanwala et al. [16] investigated the mechanism for how BCL6 repressed Blimp1 transcription, and found that BCL6 regulated the Blimp1 promoter through a novel mechanism involving AP1 elements. Specifically, BCL6 is a potent repressor of transcriptional activity mediated by AP1 factors and they found that the zinc-finger region of BCL6 interacted with c-JUN, JUNB, and JUND proteins but did not bind to c-FOS or FRA2 proteins.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of BCL family along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - BCL9-JUN-TCF7L1, BCL9-JUN-RHO and BCL9-JUN-TLE2. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of CSNK-JUN-X combinations

c-JUN (a component of the transcription factor AP1) is a phosphoprotein. In nonstimulated fibroblasts and epithelial cells, c-JUN is phosphorylated on a cluster of two to three sites abutting its DNA-binding domain, which inhibits DNA binding, and their dephosphorylation correlates with increased AP1 activity. Lin et al. [17] show that two of these sites, Thr-231 and Ser-249, are phosphorylated by casein kinase II (CKII). Substitution of the third site, Ser-243, by Phe interferes with phosphorylation of the inhibitory sites in vivo and by purified CKII in vitro. Microinjection into living cells of synthetic peptides that are specific competitive substrates or inhibitors of CKII results in induction of AP1 activity and c-JUN expression. Their results suggested that one of the roles of nuclear protein kinase CKII, is to attenuate AP1 activity through phosphorylation of c-JUN.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CSNK family along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CSNK1D-JUN-LEF1, CSNK1G1-JUN-SEN2, CSNK1G1-JUN-WNT2, CSNK1G1-JUN-TCF7L1, CSNK1G1-JUN-TLE2, CSNK1G1-JUN-KREMEN1 and CSNK1A1-JUN-TCF7L1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of CCND-JUN-X combinations

The regulation of c-JUN is complex and involves both increases in the levels of c-JUN protein as well as phosphorylation of specific serines (63 and 73) by JUN N-terminal kinase (JNK). Wisdom et al. [6] used fibroblasts derived from c-JUN null embryos to define the role of c-JUN in two separate processes: cell growth and apoptosis. They showed that in fibroblasts, c-JUN is required for the progression of cells through the G1 phase of the cell cycle by a mechanism that involves, in part, direct transcriptional control of the CCND1 gene.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of CCND family along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CCND1-JUN-SFRP4, CCND1-JUN-PITX2, CCND3-JUN-PYGO1 and CCND1-JUN-PPP2CA. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.5. Examining the behaviour of GSK3-JUN-X combinations

Lopez-Bergami et al. [18] indicate that constitutive ERK activation in melanoma cells is the primary pathway that regulates the levels of c-JUN expression, in part, by inactivating GSK3 and consequently preventing c-JUN degradation. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of GSK3 family along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - GSK3B-JUN-TLE1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.6. Examining the behaviour of PPP2-JUN-X combinations

Induction of gene expression by c-JUN involves stimulation of its transactivation ability and upregulation of DNA binding capacity. Gilan et al. [19] show that interaction of c-JUN with chromatin is positively regulated by protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A) complexes targeted to c-JUN by the PR55 α regulatory subunit. PR55 α -PP2A specifically dephosphorylates T239 of c-JUN, promoting its binding to genes regulating tumour cell migration and invasion. It also enhanced transcription of these genes, without affecting phosphorylation of c-JUN on S63. These findings suggest a critical role for interplay between JNK and PP2A pathways determining the functional activity of c-JUN/AP1 in tumour cells.

Toll-like receptor (TLR4), can be activated by LPS and induce proinflammatory cytokines to resist invasion of pathogenic microorganism, but excessive inflammation can trigger tissue injury. Recent studies found that malignant fibrous histiocytoma amplified sequence 1 (MFHAS1) suppressed the expression of cytokine IL6 in Raw264.7 cells stimulated by LPS. Shi et al. [20] investigated the role of MFHAS1 in TLR4 signaling pathway and the possible mechanisms implicated. Their results indicated that the expression of MFHAS1 was significantly increased in cells stimulated with LPS. Up-regulation of MFHAS1 effectively suppressed inflammatory cytokine expression in cells exposed to LPS, whereas down-regulation of MFHAS1 markedly increased inflammatory cytokines expression. Co-immunoprecipitation, pull-down and

immunofluorescence tests demonstrated that MFHAS1 combined with the B and C subunits of PP2A and induced cytoplasm translocation of the C subunit, leading to decrease dephosphorylation of c-JUN at Thr239 and increase degradation of c-JUN. Reduction of c-JUN protein resulted in decreased AP1 activity, which was independent of inhibition of JNK or p38MAPK phosphorylation. Taken together, their results indicated that MFHAS1 suppresses TLR4 signaling pathway through induction of PP2A C subunit cytoplasm translocation and subsequent c-JUN degradation, leading finally to decrease AP1 activity and cytokines expression.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of PPP2 family along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DKK1-JUN-PPP2R1A, DKK1-JUN-PPP2CA, DVL2-JUN-PPP2R1A, CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2CA, CTNNBIP1-JUN-PPP2R1A, DVL2-JUN-PPP2CA, FRZB-JUN-PPP2CA and CCND1-JUN-PPP2CA. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.7. Examining the behaviour of DVL-JUN-X combinations

Dishevelled (DSH/DVL) proteins mediate WNT signaling by up-regulating β -catenin levels and stimulating T cell factor (TCF)/LEF1-dependent transcription. Li et al. [21] identified a new DVL-mediated signaling pathway in that mouse DVL proteins, when expressed in COS-7 cells, stimulate c-JUN-dependent transcription activity and the kinase activity of the c-JUN N-terminal kinase (JNK). The DEP domain of DVL1 is essential for JNK activation. By contrast, all three conserved domains of DVL, including DIX, PDZ, and DEP, are required for up-regulation of β -catenin and for stimulation of LEF-1-mediated transcription in mammalian cells. Thus, they report that DVL activates JNK and regulates c-JUN-dependent gene transcription in addition to its ability to regulate the β -catenin and LEF1 pathways.

Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of DVL family along with JUN, to be prominent at 3rd order level - DVL2-JUN-SEN2, DVL2-JUN-TCF7L1, DVL2-JUN-TLE2, DVL2-JUN-KREMEN1, DVL2-JUN-PITX2, DVL2-JUN-WNT2B, DVL2-JUN-TCF7, DVL2-JUN-PPP2R1A, DVL1-JUN-WNT2B, DVL2-JUN-WIF1, DVL2-JUN-SFRP1, DVL1-JUN-SEN2, DVL2-JUN-FBXW4, DVL2-JUN-WNT4, DVL2-JUN-WNT2, DVL2-JUN-TLE1, DVL2-JUN-WNT3A, DVL2-JUN-PPP2CA and DVL2-JUN-WNT5A. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of JUN in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the JUN, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

Acknowledgments

Special thanks to Mrs. Rita Sinha and late Mr. Prabhat Sinha for supporting the author financially, without which this work could not have been made possible.

Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For JUN, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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